

Appendix 1. Estimates of probability of presence (p_p ; \pm 95% credible intervals) of radio-tagged Kittlitz's murrelets by window length (1-, 3-, 5-, 7-day, and 15-day) and boat survey (survey 1=orange, survey 2=teal), Icy Bay, Alaska, 1–15 July 2007–2012. Asterisks indicate windows when the same telemetry data were used to estimate p_p for boat surveys 1 and 2.

Appendix 2. Number of telemetry locations of Kittlitz's murrelets by year and (a) spatial state and (b) Bowditch ice class, 1–15 July 2007–2012, Icy Bay, Alaska. We did not locate any murrelets in very close pack ice.

Appendix 3. Kittlitz's murrelet annual abundance estimates and 95% credible intervals (black) and corresponding coefficients of variation (blue) without probability of presence (p_p ; None; statistical population) and with p_p by window length (1-, 3-, 5-, and 7-day; biological population) around corresponding boat surveys and entire window (15-day) when boat surveys were conducted (i.e. 1–15 July), Icy Bay, Alaska. We completed two boat surveys each year except 2009 when only one survey was done.

Appendix 4. Posterior distributions of mean r , the instantaneous growth rate, across all years for the statistical and biological populations of the Kittlitz's murrelet in Icy Bay, Alaska, 2005–2017.